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Online aggression in Czech adolescents: prevalence, demographic variation, and platform-related risk

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This study examines the prevalence and patterns of online aggression among Czech adolescents, including emerging forms such as AI-generated sexual imagery, using a large cross-sectional school-based survey of 42,772 respondents aged 13–17 conducted in 2025. Data were collected via an anonymous online questionnaire capturing 13 behaviourally specific forms of online aggression, and analysed primarily using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, effect sizes, and a respondent-fixed-effects logistic regression model for platform-specific risk. The results show that online aggression is highly prevalent, with verbal aggression reported by 58.6% of adolescents and 31.9% experiencing regular exposure; notable findings include the emergence of AI-generated nude imagery (7.3%), higher prevalence in vocational school tracks, and a robust association between platform use intensity and reported harm. These findings suggest that online aggression represents a widespread and multifaceted risk affecting adolescents, extending beyond traditional cyberbullying definitions, with important implications for prevention, policy, and the need to address AI-enabled forms of harm and low rates of disclosure among victims.

KEYWORDS

adolescents, AI-generated sexual imagery, cyberbullying, online aggression, verbal harassment

Introduction

The digital environment has become an integral part of adolescents' everyday lives, shaping communication, social interaction, and self-presentation. While digital technologies provide many opportunities, they also expose young people to a range of online risks.

The most common types of risky situations that children encounter in the online environment include various forms of *online aggression*, such as insults, humiliation, threats, blackmail, and the dissemination of degrading or dishonouring materials in the form of text, photographs, or videos. In the present study, *online aggression* is conceptualised as a broad umbrella category covering diverse harmful digital experiences. *Cyberbullying*, by contrast, is understood as a narrower subset of online aggression characterised primarily by repetition, persistence, intensity, frequent anonymity, and the potential for rapid and wide-reaching dissemination. This broader

conceptual framing is analytically useful because serious forms of harm, such as image-based abuse, extortion, or AI-generated sexualised imagery, may occur even in the absence of repeated attacks and therefore may not always fit classical definitions of cyberbullying. Online aggression and cyberbullying among children have been widely studied for more than two decades (Cowie, 2009; Hollá, 2013; Kopecký and Szotkowski, 2014, 2015; Patchin and Hinduja, 2015; Pridgen, 2009; Sabella et al., 2013; Santre, 2022) and draw attention to both the high prevalence and its impact on the mental state of children and the need to implement various types of preventive and intervention measures.

For example, the 2021 *Cyberbullying Data study* (Hinduja and Patchin, 2021) analyzed data collected in April 2019 from a representative sample of 4,972 primary and secondary school students aged 12–17 in the US, and the results showed that 17.4% of respondents reported experiencing cyberbullying as a victim, while 4.9% admitted to committing it themselves. A follow-up survey by the Cyberbullying Research Center in 2024 (Hinduja and Patchin, 2024) processed data from 5,005 American schoolchildren aged 13–17, collected in May and June 2023. According to these results, 26.5% of respondents said they had been a victim of cyberbullying in the last 30 days, reflecting the current prevalence rate among the adolescent population.

At the same time, research confirms that the prevalence of cyberbullying among adolescents is not consistent – according to systematic reviews, the incidence of cyberbullying from the victim's perspective ranges from 13.99% and 57.5%, while the prevalence of perpetrators ranges between 6.0% and 46.3%. These differences are influenced by a number of individual factors, such as age, gender or previous experience of victimisation, as well as contextual factors – such as the quality of family relationships, school climate or geographical environment (Zhu et al., 2021). The chosen methodology of the research study also has a significant impact – in a broader sense, almost any aggressive behavior in the online environment can be considered cyberbullying, while a narrower definition understands it as actions that meet specific criteria, such as repetition, intensity or severe impact on the victim (Hollá, 2016; Kopecký, 2016; Kopecký and Szotkowski, 2017).

Data are also available on the so-called *lifetime prevalence of cyberbullying*, i.e., the occurrence of this phenomenon at any time in the respondent's life so far. For example, in the US, according to repeated surveys, the proportion of adolescents who have experienced cyberbullying at some point in their lives is increasing – while in 2007 about 18% of high school students reported this experience, in 2019 it was already around 36% (López-Vizcaíno et al., 2021). This increase can be partly explained by the increasing use of digital technologies, mobile devices and social networks among children and young people (López-Vizcaíno et al., 2021).

However, the use of *lifetime prevalence* in the context of adolescent development is the subject of criticism. These data are based on a variety of studies using different methodological approaches, which complicates their comparison. As Kopecký (2016) points out, lifetime data can distort the actual occurrence of cyberbullying, as the time period is not uniform among respondents – for some it may be an experience several months old, for others it may be a childhood event. From a methodological point of view, it is therefore preferable to focus

on the occurrence of cyberbullying in a well-defined time frame, ideally in the last few weeks or months, which allows for more accurate cross-study and cross-national comparisons.

Considering these conceptual and methodological issues, the present study uses the term *online aggression* as a broader umbrella concept referring to a heterogeneous set of harmful online experiences, including verbal harassment, image-based abuse, threats, impersonation, and AI-generated sexual imagery. The term *cyberbullying* is reserved for a narrower subset of these behaviours that more closely aligns with core definitional criteria, especially repetition and sustained victimization. This distinction allows us to capture both the broader ecology of digital harm and the more specific pattern of chronic victimization traditionally associated with cyberbullying.

Impacts of online aggression on youth

The harmful effects of online aggression – especially verbal harassment and humiliation – on students' well-being are well documented. Being the target of online insults, threats, or ridicule can lead to severe psychological distress. Victimized adolescents consistently report higher levels of *depressive symptoms, anxiety, loneliness, and low self-esteem* compared to their peers (Nixon, 2014; Zhu et al., 2021). In fact, one review noted that youth bullied online show greater depression and anxiety than those bullied offline, alongside increased feelings of isolation (Zhu et al., 2021). Victims may also develop psychosomatic issues (e.g., headaches, stomach aches) and in extreme cases may experience suicidal ideation (Nixon, 2014). Self-esteem often suffers profoundly – constant derogatory messages can make young people doubt their worth and withdraw socially. School performance can be affected as well: studies have found links between cyberbullying victimization and school absenteeism or declining academic achievement, as students fear encountering harassment or feel too distressed to focus on school (Zhu et al., 2021). Not only do victims suffer; those who perpetrate online aggression are also at risk for negative outcomes like increased aggression and delinquent behavior offline (Nixon, 2014). The classroom environment can deteriorate if verbal aggression spills over from online to in-person relationships, eroding trust and a sense of safety among students. Crucially, the psychological harm from online verbal aggression can be long-lasting. Unlike face-to-face interactions, harmful online content may remain accessible or be repeatedly shared, potentially prolonging victims' distress. This perpetual visibility intensifies feelings of humiliation and powerlessness in victims. Over time, chronic exposure to such aggression may contribute to clinical problems in adolescents such as chronic depression, post-traumatic stress, or disordered eating. In sum, verbal cyber-aggression is far from “harmless banter” – it poses a serious threat to students' mental health and development, warranting effective prevention and support measures in schools (Zhu et al., 2021).

In recent years, generative artificial intelligence has begun to interfere with the above-mentioned forms of risky behavior, enabling the creation of realistic photographs and videos using the actual appearance of specific individuals (so-called deep fakes). In practice, this means that anyone can misuse anyone else's identity

and create material that can be easily misused for cyberbullying and other forms of aggression. Particularly dangerous forms of this behavior include so-called *deep nudes* (“undressing applications”) – technologies that can create realistic “photographs” of naked people (Kopecký and Voráč, 2025).

Methods

Study context

The research *Czech Pupils in the Online World* was carried out by the Institute for Research and Education in the Digital Technologies and Cybersecurity of the Faculty of Education, Palacký University in Olomouc as part of a contract research (contract number PDF_2025_0120) with CZ. NIC, z. s. p. o., which is the coordinator of the Safer Internet Centre Czech Republic.

Research procedure

This cross-sectional study was conducted using a large-scale school-based survey design covering the entire Czech Republic. Recruitment involved several steps. First, all primary and secondary school principals and teachers listed in the InRED 2.0 database were contacted. The database includes approximately 90,000 contacts and represents roughly half of all teachers in the Czech Republic.

Data collection followed a multi-step consent process. School management first approved participation, after which parental informed consent was obtained through cooperating teachers. Respondents then provided their own consent prior to completing the questionnaire.

The survey was administered anonymously using an online questionnaire implemented through Google Forms and the Researcher 2.0 data collection platform. Data collection took place during regular school lessons between 1 April 2025 and 15 May 2025.

Sample characteristics

After data cleaning (removal of implausible ages and inconsistent responses), the dataset was restricted to respondents aged 13–17 years. The final analytical sample consisted of 42,772 participants. Girls comprised 52.18% of the sample ($n = 22,319$) and boys 47.82% ($n = 20,453$). The modal age was 14 years and the mean age was 14.81 years. A graphical depiction of the number of respondents is shown in Figure 1.

To assess sample representativeness, the distribution of respondents was compared with population data from the Czech Statistical Office. The sex and school-type distributions closely matched national population parameters. The deviation in sex distribution was approximately 1%. Regional discrepancies ranged between 5% and 8%, particularly in Prague and the South Moravian Region. Given the large sample size, these deviations were considered substantively negligible. Moreover, the phenomena under investigation occur primarily in online environments that transcend regional boundaries and are therefore unlikely to be strongly shaped by geographic location.

Research instrument

The survey instrument included a set of behaviourally specific items designed to capture different forms of online aggression

FIGURE 1
Number of respondents (boys and girls) by age. $N = 42,772$.

experienced by adolescents. The items were developed by the research team and subsequently reviewed by experts in cyberbullying, digital safety, and adolescent psychology. The expert review focused on clarity, relevance, and age appropriateness of the items, resulting in minor wording adjustments. This process contributed to the content validity of the instrument.

The study was primarily exploratory in nature. Instead of testing directional hypotheses, the study addressed several research questions aimed at describing the scope, frequency, and contextual characteristics of online aggression experienced by adolescents.

Specifically, the study examined:

- (RQ1) the prevalence and frequency of various forms of online aggression, including verbal insults, image-based abuse, AI-generated sexual imagery, and impersonation;
- (RQ2) the identity of perpetrators (e.g., peers, strangers);
- (RQ3) demographic differences in victimization patterns across age, sex, and school type;
- (RQ4) the association between the intensity of social media use and the likelihood of reporting online aggression on the same platform;
- (RQ5) the overlap between victims and self-reported perpetrators of online aggression;
- (RQ6) the coping strategies victims employed in response to these experiences.

Measures

Online aggression was measured using thirteen behaviourally specific items covering verbal, relational, image-based, identity-related, and technology-mediated harms, including a specific item on AI-generated nude imagery. Each item represented a separate behavioural incident rather than an indicator of a single latent construct.

Because the items represent heterogeneous forms of victimisation rather than manifestations of one underlying scale, internal consistency measures such as Cronbach's α were not calculated. Instead, each form of online aggression was analysed separately, following established practice in international prevalence studies (e.g., EU Kids Online, Cyberbullying Research Center, Pew Research Center).

To approximate the distinction between general exposure to online aggression and more persistent victimisation consistent with cyberbullying, two operational indicators were constructed. Overall exposure captured whether the respondent experienced a given behaviour at least once during the past 12 months. Regular exposure was operationalised as experiencing the given behaviour three times per month or more frequently (responses: *about 3 times a month, about once a week, several times a week*). The exact wording of the survey items and response categories is provided in [Appendix A](#).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were first used to estimate the prevalence of different forms of online

aggression reported by respondents during the past 12 months. Given the exploratory nature of the study and its focus on mapping the scope and distribution of online victimisation experiences, the primary analytical strategy relied on descriptive prevalence estimates and group comparisons across key demographic categories.

Associations between categorical variables (e.g., sex, age group, and school type) and specific forms of online aggression were examined using chi-square tests of independence. Because of the large sample size, statistical significance alone could overstate the practical importance of observed differences. Therefore, effect sizes were systematically reported to aid interpretation of substantive significance. For 2×2 contingency tables, effect sizes were expressed using the phi coefficient (ϕ), while Cramér's V was used for larger contingency tables.

In addition to statistical significance testing, selected analyses also report risk ratios and percentage-point differences in order to facilitate interpretation of age-related trends and prevalence differences between groups. These measures provide a more intuitive representation of the magnitude of observed differences.

To examine platform-specific risk, an additional logistic regression model was estimated at the respondent-platform level, with a binary indicator of whether the respondent reported having experienced online harassment or harm on a given platform during the past year (1 = yes, 0 = no) as the outcome. This platform-specific outcome was linked to the corresponding measure of frequency of use of the same platform, measured on a four-point scale (0 = never, 1 = sometimes, 2 = often, 3 = all the time). For this purpose, the data were restructured into platform-level long format, yielding one observation per respondent-platform combination. After excluding observations with missing data and omitting Signal because of insufficient variation in the outcome, the final analytic file comprised 556,036 observations. To reduce bias from stable between-respondent differences, the model included respondent-specific indicator terms. Platform was entered as a categorical predictor, with Discord serving as the reference category for estimation purposes. This modelling approach should be understood as an exploratory adjustment for stable between-respondent differences rather than as a fully specified multilevel panel model.

Given that the study examines multiple forms of online aggression across several demographic dimensions, the analyses involve a large number of statistical comparisons. Because the research is exploratory and aims primarily to describe patterns of victimisation rather than test a small number of predefined hypotheses, the results are interpreted cautiously. Particular emphasis is placed on the magnitude and consistency of observed patterns rather than solely on p -values.

Results

The most common form of online aggression is *verbal harm* (insults, name-calling), experienced by approximately 58.6% of students. Substantial proportions also reported sharing of humiliating photos (34.4%), threats or intimidation (26.0%), harassment by repeated calling (24.2%), and sharing of humiliating videos (18.1%). A newly emerging phenomenon in the results is the misuse of *AI-generated nude photos*. 7.3% of

respondents reported that an AI-generated nude image of them had been created. While this phenomenon does not yet reach the frequency of traditional forms of aggression, its potential impacts can be very serious. Among children who reported that an AI-generated nude image of them had been created, 68.81% also indicated that they had experienced extortion. The proportion was even higher among boys (73.22%) compared to girls (60.05%).

Sex differences in online aggression and cyberbullying

Within the broader spectrum of online aggression, cyberbullying represents a narrower pattern of repeated and more sustained victimization. It is typically defined by key criteria such as repetition, intensity, and a meaningful impact on the victim, distinguishing it from isolated incidents of online aggression. For this reason, we examined these factors in our dataset to estimate how many respondents experienced regular exposure to online aggression (see Measures for the operationalization of this indicator), which may approximate patterns typically associated with cyberbullying.

When the criterion is restricted to regular exposure, boys surpass girls, and the reduction from overall to regular prevalence is substantially larger among girls. Overall, girls reported verbal aggression more frequently than boys (62.38% vs. 54.53%; $p < .001$; $\phi = .080$). However, at the level of regular exposure this difference reversed, with boys slightly exceeding girls (24.11% vs. 22.84%; $p = .002$; $\phi = .015$). This reversal suggests a modest but statistically reliable shift toward more recurrent exposure among boys.

A similar pattern was observed for sexualized and technologically mediated forms of aggression: boys showed substantially higher regular exposure than girls for both sharing of intimate images (5.14% vs. 2.02%; $p < .001$; $\phi = .085$) and AI-generated nude images (5.19% vs. 2.07%; $p < .001$; $\phi = .084$).

Overall, 31.88% of respondents reported regular exposure to online aggression. Regular exposure was slightly more prevalent among boys (32.80%) than among girls (31.05%). Given the repeated nature of these experiences, this level of exposure may already reflect patterns consistent with cyberbullying (Table 1).

Age differences

Analyses of the five most prevalent forms of online aggression showed that these behaviors are common across all age groups, with only modest age gradients. Verbally aggressive behavior was reported by approximately 59% of respondents overall and was already highly prevalent at age 13, increasing only slightly by age 17 (risk ratio ≈ 1.04 ; absolute difference ≈ 2 percentage points). In contrast, more visually and relationally mediated behaviours, such as the sharing of embarrassing photos and videos or repeated harassing calls, exhibited somewhat stronger age-related patterns: for example, the prevalence of having an embarrassing photo shared increased from roughly 29% at age 13 to 35% at age 17 (risk ratio ≈ 1.20 ; absolute difference ≈ 6 percentage points), and similar relative increases were observed for embarrassing videos and harassing calls. Statistical tests of association between age (13–17) and each aggression type yielded highly significant chi-square results, as expected given the large sample size; however, Cramér’s V -values were very small (approximately 0.02–0.06), indicating that age explains

TABLE 1 Frequency of online harassment incidents and Sex differences.

Types of online aggression experienced by children	Percent of respondents (total)	Sex difference (total)	Percent of respondents (regular)	Sex difference (regular)
Verbal aggression (insults, mockery)	58.62%	7.86%	23.45%	-1.27%
Shared an embarrassing photo	34.35%	2.80%	10.16%	-1.03%
Shared your intimate photo	6.78%	-3.76%	3.51%	-3.12%
AI-generated nude image	7.29%	-3.25%	3.56%	-3.13%
Shared an embarrassing video	18.15%	-2.67%	6.18%	-2.38%
Shared an embarrassing audio	13.85%	-3.93%	5.21%	-2.93%
Abused online account	12.00%	-1.34%	4.45%	-2.22%
Threatened or intimidated	26.04%	3.86%	8.91%	-1.24%
Scammed (shopping, auctions)	14.05%	-4.43%	4.21%	-3.29%
Blackmailed	15.16%	3.71%	5.86%	-0.64%
Accessed account without permission	15.81%	-1.88%	4.59%	-2.65%
Harassed by repeated calls	24.23%	2.74%	9.88%	-0.34%
Created a fake profile of you	15.12%	0.14%	4.98%	-1.62%

$N = 42,772$.

The table presents the prevalence of different forms of online aggression experienced during the past 12 months. “Percent total” indicates the proportion of respondents who reported each form of aggression at least once. “Difference between sex (total)” indicates the percentage-point difference in prevalence between girls and boys. “Percent regular” indicates the proportion of respondents who reported repeated exposure, operationalised as experiencing the given behaviour at least three times per month. This repeated exposure is used here as a proxy indicator of victimisation consistent with cyberbullying. “Difference between sex (regular)” indicates the percentage-point difference between girls and boys in this repeated exposure. Positive values indicate higher prevalence among girls, whereas negative values indicate higher prevalence among boys.

only a limited proportion of the variance in exposure to these behaviours. Overall, online aggression appears widespread throughout early and mid-adolescence, with age-related differences that are statistically detectable but substantively small, and somewhat more pronounced for image- and video-based forms than for verbal aggression. These age-related trends are visualized in Figure 2.

School differences

Focusing exclusively on upper-secondary students, we compared three distinct school tracks in terms of the five most prevalent forms of online aggression. The analysed tracks comprised upper-secondary vocational schools without a school-leaving examination, upper-secondary vocational schools with a school-leaving examination and four-year academic grammar schools. Across almost all aggression types, students attending both types of vocational schools reported higher prevalence rates than their peers in four-year grammar schools, although the magnitude of these differences varied by aggression form. Verbal online aggression was highly prevalent in all tracks, but it was most frequently reported by students in vocational schools with a school-leaving exam (approximately 63%), followed by vocational schools without a school-leaving exam (about 60%), and least frequently by students in four-year grammar schools (around 54%). A similar, somewhat smaller, gradient was observed for the sharing of embarrassing photos and videos, where both vocational tracks showed higher

prevalence than four-year grammar schools, with the largest difference for embarrassing videos (approximately 23% in vocational schools without school-leaving exam compared to about 17% in four-year grammar schools). The most pronounced between-track differences emerged for online threats and intimidation: more than one third of students in vocational schools without school-leaving exam reported having experienced threats or intimidation, whereas the corresponding prevalence was roughly one quarter in vocational schools with school-leaving exam and below one fifth in four-years grammar schools. In contrast, repeated harassing phone calls exhibited very similar prevalence levels across all three tracks, indicating that this specific form of aggression is pervasive regardless of school track. The comparison is visualized in Figure 3.

Perpetrators

The analysis also focused on identifying the individuals who perpetrate attacks against pupils in online environments. The data show that the most frequent aggressors are classmates from the same class, reported by 14.67% of respondents. The second most common category includes former friends (11.98%), indicating that interpersonal conflicts often continue even after the termination of a relationship or friendship. A considerable proportion of attacks are also committed by individuals whom the child knows only from the internet (9.65%). Additional aggressors include students from other schools (7.45%) and classmates from other classes within the same school (6.70%).

FIGURE 2 Frequency of the top 5 online harassment by age. N differs according to the age: 13 years: N = 7,550; 14 years: N = 11,285; 15 years: N = 11,248; 16 years: N = 7,228; 17 years: N = 5,461.

FIGURE 3

Prevalence of the five most common forms of online aggression by secondary school type. N differs according to the school type: Upper-secondary school without school-leaving exam: $N = 2,647$; Vocational upper-secondary school with school-leaving exam: $N = 6,619$; Four-year academic grammar school: $N = 1,656$.

Coping and help-seeking strategies

The analysis examined how children and adolescents dealt with experiences of online harassment in the full sample. In total, 12,509 respondents (29.2%) reported that they did not tell anyone about the harassment. A further 5,512 respondents (12.9%) indicated that they told their parents, whereas 1,481 respondents (3.5%) reported that they informed a teacher or the school. Only 1,058 respondents (2.5%) stated that they called a helpline, 1,489 respondents (3.5%) reported that they contacted the police, and 1,038 respondents (2.4%) indicated that they used an online counselling service. An additional 1,414 respondents (3.3%) described using some other, unspecified way of dealing with the situation.

Comparative risk of social media platforms

A respondent-platform logistic model with respondent fixed effects showed that more intensive use of a platform was strongly associated with a higher likelihood of reporting harassment or harm on that same platform during the past year. Each one-step increase in frequency of use was associated with a 3.41-fold increase in the odds of reporting a harmful experience.

Differences between platforms remained substantial after adjustment for frequency of use and stable between-respondent differences. Relative to Discord, higher odds of reported harm were observed for Instagram (OR = 4.66) and Snapchat (OR = 1.68). Lower odds were found for WhatsApp (OR = 0.77), TikTok (OR = 0.59), Messenger and Telegram (both OR about 0.40), Facebook and SMS/MMS (both OR about 0.26–0.27), X (OR = 0.21), e-mail (OR = 0.11), and YouTube (OR = 0.06). Reddit showed a near-zero estimated odds ratio, indicating very low reported prevalence of harm in this model.

Discussion

A core contribution of this study is the explicit separation of *online aggression* as a broad umbrella of harmful digital experiences from *cyberbullying* as a narrower pattern of repeated and sustained victimization. This distinction matters empirically: several severe harms documented in our data (e.g., extortion, impersonation/account abuse, or AI-generated sexualised imagery) can be episodic yet highly consequential and may therefore be missed by cyberbullying definitions that require repetition and persistence. At the same time, the study preserves analytical space for more chronic victimization by operationalising recurrent exposure as a proxy indicator of cyberbullying-like experiences.

The prevalence estimates underscore that online aggression is widespread among Czech adolescents. Using behaviourally specific items covering 13 distinct harms, verbal aggression was the most common experience. Importantly, when recurrent exposure (≥ 3 times per month) was used to approximate more persistent victimization, nearly one third of respondents (31.9%) reported regular exposure to at least one form of online aggression. This proportion should not be interpreted as a direct prevalence estimate of cyberbullying in the strict definitional sense, because our proxy does not capture all core criteria (e.g., power imbalance or intentionality). However, it does indicate that a substantial share of adolescents are not only encountering isolated incidents but are embedded in patterns of repeated digital victimization that resemble the chronicity typically associated with cyberbullying (Langos, 2012).

Cross-study comparisons need caution because prevalence estimates are highly sensitive to definitional and measurement choices. Prior reviews document wide variation in cyberbullying victimization rates across countries and studies, and they highlight that verbal forms of abuse tend to be among the most

common. This supports interpreting our high prevalence of verbal aggression as partly reflecting the broad operationalization and behaviourally specific measurement strategy used to capture a wider ecology of harm rather than only “classical” cyberbullying episodes (Zhu et al., 2021).

A particularly novel finding is the emergence of AI-generated sexual imagery as a tool for harassment. Over 7% of students reported encountering a fake nude photo of themselves created with AI. Ciardha et al. (2025) indicate that the widespread availability of open diffusion models since 2021–2022 has substantially lowered the barriers to producing synthetic sexually explicit materials. One in ten adolescents reported knowing a peer who had used generative AI to create explicit images of another minor, suggesting a rapid normalization of such practices (Thorn, 2024). Motivations for generating synthetic images range from curiosity and peer pressure to intentional harassment or retaliation. In this sense, generative AI enables the transformation of everyday or fantasized notions about peers into reproducible and potentially viral content, thereby fundamentally reshaping the dynamics of peer-inflicted harm.

The policy relevance of AI-enabled sexualised harms is particularly salient in the Czech context. Recent amendments to Czech criminal law (effective 1 January 2026) include a new offence addressing the non-consensual use of a person’s identity for the production and dissemination of pornography (§ 191a of the Criminal Code), which is directly relevant to deepfake pornography and related non-consensual synthetic imagery (Sedova, 2026). While legal change alone does not prevent victimization, the combination of documented prevalence, strong overlap with extortion, and the rapid diffusion of “nudify” tools supports the need for clear institutional procedures for reporting, evidence preservation, and rapid response in schools and child-safety services.

Sex patterns in the data were nuanced. Girls reported higher overall exposure to verbal aggression, yet boys showed slightly higher recurrent exposure (our proxy for more persistent victimization) and substantially higher recurrent exposure to sexualized and technologically mediated harms (including AI-generated nude imagery). This “reversal” pattern warrants a cautious interpretation. One plausible explanation is heterogeneity in types of exposure: girls may be more likely to encounter isolated or less persistent verbal harassment, whereas boys may be more likely to become involved in recurrent cycles of victimization. However, an alternative explanation is methodological and social: boys and girls may differ in reporting thresholds, social desirability concerns, or the perceived seriousness of repeated victimization, which could shape self-reports in ways that contribute to the observed pattern. This interpretation aligns with broader evidence that gender differences in cybervictimization are often small and context-dependent, and that measurement choices can influence observed sex/gender gaps (Kasturiratna et al., 2025).

Age differences were statistically detectable but substantively small, suggesting that online aggression is common across early and mid-adolescence rather than being concentrated in a narrow age window. This is broadly compatible with the idea that as adolescents’ internet and social media engagement increases, opportunities for exposure to online aggression also increase,

even if age itself explains only a small portion of variance within a restricted 13–17 range.

School-track differences showed a consistent pattern: adolescents in vocational tracks generally reported higher prevalence than those in academic grammar schools. Our design does not allow us to test mechanisms behind this gradient, but the finding is consistent with a socio-ecological interpretation in which peer-group dynamics and features of the school environment shape exposure and escalation. Meta-analytic evidence suggests that more positive school climate is associated with lower cyberbullying victimization, supporting the plausibility that school-level relational environments may contribute to differences in online aggression risk across educational contexts. Future work should explicitly test school-level mechanisms (e.g., school climate, peer norms, teacher support) rather than relying on track differences as a proxy (Li et al., 2025).

Finally, the platform analysis suggests a robust association between frequency of platform use and self-reported harm on the same platform. A respondent–platform logistic model with respondent fixed effects indicates that, within individuals, higher frequency of use is associated with substantially higher odds of reporting harmful experiences on that platform. Importantly, this should not be interpreted as a causal claim that platform use “produces” harm; reverse causality and unmeasured time-varying factors remain plausible. Nevertheless, the finding is consistent with large cross-national evidence that intense and problematic social media use are associated with cyber-bullying outcomes and merit prevention attention. After adjustment for frequency of use and stable between-respondent differences, differences across platforms remained visible, suggesting that platform affordances, communication norms, and user audiences may contribute to variation in reported harm (Craig et al., 2020).

From an adolescent mental health and wellbeing perspective, our findings suggest that online aggression may function for a subset of young people as a persistent and difficult-to-escape stressor: high levels of regular exposure combined with low disclosure indicate that many adolescents may be managing ongoing psychological strain without timely support from adults or formal services (Daneback et al., 2018; Dennehy et al., 2020). Qualitative evidence highlights the pervasive and intrusive nature of digital communication, which can amplify rumination, feelings of entrapment, and escalation of distress, while barriers to help-seeking frequently include lack of trust, fears of worsening the situation, and expectations of inadequate responses from adults or schools (Daneback et al., 2018; Dennehy et al., 2020). Meta-analytic syntheses consistently show that cyberbullying and online victimization are associated with elevated risk of internalizing difficulties—particularly depressive and anxiety symptoms—as well as a broader range of adverse psychological outcomes; importantly, these associations are understood as potentially bidirectional, with pre-existing vulnerabilities increasing the likelihood of victimization and victimization further exacerbating mental health problems (Kasturiratna et al., 2025).

Particular concern has recently been raised in relation to AI-generated sexualized images (e.g., “deep nudes”) and related coercive practices. Emerging literature suggests that such forms of abuse may intensify harm by combining loss of control over

one's body and reputation with rapid scalability and long-term persistence of content online, although empirical evidence in this area remains limited and continues to develop (Jose and Mathew, 2025). The observed overlap with extortion in our data is consistent with broader evidence indicating that sexual extortion of minors is associated with a range of short- and long-term harms, including psychological injury and increased vulnerability to further victimization (Wolbers et al., 2025). In practical terms, these patterns underscore the importance of school-embedded prevention and early identification efforts, including trusted and accessible reporting pathways, clear safeguarding protocols, and available counselling support, given evidence that interventions can reduce both cyberbullying perpetration and victimization (Polanin et al., 2022).

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. First, although the sample is very large and geographically broad, recruitment occurred through schools and teacher networks rather than probability sampling. This may lead to selection effects (e.g., differential participation by schools, teachers, or student groups), and adolescents not regularly attending school may be underrepresented.

Second, the data rely on self-report in a 12-month reference window. Recall bias and social desirability effects are plausible, particularly for sensitive experiences such as AI-generated nude imagery, extortion, or sexualized victimization. Misinterpretation of items is also possible despite behaviourally specific wording and expert review.

Third, the instrument was designed to cover heterogeneous forms of online aggression rather than measure a single latent construct. Consequently, the study does not estimate internal consistency metrics such as Cronbach's alpha, and single-item measurement may still contain item-specific measurement error. We address transparency concerns by providing the full wording and response categories in Appendix A, but formal psychometric validation remains a goal for future research.

Fourth, the operationalisation of "regular exposure" (≥ 3 times per month) is an approximation intended to capture repeated victimization patterns. It should not be interpreted as a definitive prevalence estimate of cyberbullying because the operational definition does not incorporate all definitional criteria (e.g., power imbalance, intentionality, or perceived impact).

Fifth, due to the large sample size and the breadth of outcomes examined, multiple comparisons increase the risk of detecting statistically significant but practically negligible differences. We therefore emphasize effect sizes and substantive magnitudes rather than p -values alone.

Finally, the platform analysis is cross-sectional and based on self-reported harm "on a given platform" over the prior year. Although respondent fixed effects reduce bias from stable between-person differences, causal inference remains limited. Platform differences may reflect a mixture of usage patterns, platform affordances, and reporting behaviour rather than intrinsic platform risk.

Implications for practice and policy

The findings imply several actionable priorities grounded directly in the observed victimization patterns. First, because perpetrators are often classmates or former friends, prevention efforts should be anchored in peer and school-community dynamics (e.g., conflict escalation, norm-setting, bystander roles) rather than focusing exclusively on anonymous online threats. Improving school climate and relational safety is a plausible leverage point, given meta-analytic evidence linking more positive school climate with lower cybervictimization (Li et al., 2025).

Second, the size of the disclosure gap indicates that support systems must be designed for non-reporting by default. Schools should provide low-threshold reporting pathways, confidential counselling options, and clear guidance for students and caregivers on evidence preservation and escalation routes, especially in cases involving sexualised content and extortion.

Third, AI-generated nude imagery should be treated as an explicit prevention and response domain rather than an add-on to "traditional" cyberbullying content. The combination of measurable prevalence, high co-occurrence with extortion, and rapid diffusion of "nudify" technologies supports integrating AI-related image abuse into school policies, digital safety curricula, and child-protection protocols.

Fourth, ongoing legal and regulatory updates should be closely linked to the harms observed in adolescents' lives. In the Czech context, amendments effective from 1 January 2026 include a new criminal offence addressing non-consensual identity misuse for pornography production and dissemination (§ 191a), which is relevant to deepfake pornography. A practical implication is the need for clear institutional procedures for responding to reports, including coordination between schools, parents, platforms, and law enforcement when extortion or sexualised imagery is involved.

Finally, evidence syntheses suggest that cyberbullying prevention and intervention programs can produce small but meaningful reductions in victimization and perpetration (Gaffney et al., 2019). Given the scale of exposure in our data, even modest effect sizes may translate into substantial population benefit if programs are well implemented and updated to address emerging AI-enabled harms.

Future directions

The present study highlights several avenues for future research that are increasingly urgent given the rapid evolution of adolescents' online environments. First, the emergence of AI-generated sexual imagery as a distinct and growing form of online aggression warrants deeper investigation. Longitudinal studies are needed to determine whether exposure to such synthetic victimisation increases over time, how it interacts with other risks such as extortion, and whether its psychological impact differs from that of authentic image-based abuse. Experimental or qualitative work could further clarify adolescents' ability to distinguish between real and fabricated content and how this uncertainty shapes fear, shame, or disclosure behaviour.

Second, although demographic differences were statistically detectable, their substantive magnitude was small. Future research should therefore focus on mechanisms rather than simple group comparisons. For example, examining the mediating role of peer dynamics, school climate, impulsivity, or digital literacy may help explain why some adolescents become embroiled in recurrent aggression while others do not. Multilevel and intersectional models could illuminate how gender, school track, and online habits combine to create distinct risk profiles.

Third, the finding that nearly one third of victims did not disclose their experience underscores a critical gap in help-seeking behaviour. Future studies should explore barriers to disclosure, including fears of overreaction by adults, concerns about device confiscation, social stigma, or minimization of harm. Understanding these barriers may inform more nuanced prevention strategies that move beyond generic anti-bullying messages toward interventions tailored to adolescents' actual reasoning and constraints.

A fourth priority involves disentangling the relationship between platform use intensity and victimisation. The present design does not allow for causal inference, and it remains unclear whether high use increases exposure, whether victimisation drives adolescents to spend more time online, or whether underlying factors such as loneliness, peer conflict, or sensation seeking explain both patterns. Longitudinal or ecological momentary assessment (EMA) designs could capture fluctuations in online behaviour and victimisation risk within shorter time windows.

Fifth, as online aggression increasingly blends with offline dynamics, future research should incorporate cross-contextual measures. For example, analysing how classroom climate, teacher–student relationships, or parental mediation strategies moderate online harms could strengthen the ecological validity of future models. Linking survey data with school-level indicators or peer network structures would also allow finer-grained analysis of perpetrator networks, escalation patterns, and the transition from occasional incidents to sustained cyberbullying.

Finally, given the speed at which generative AI tools and social media platforms evolve, there is a growing need for adaptive methodological frameworks. Continuous updating of measurement instruments—particularly to capture new behaviours such as synthetic blackmail, manipulated voice recordings, or chatbot-enabled harassment—will be essential to maintain comparability and relevance. Collaboration between researchers, educators, policymakers, and technology developers will be crucial in designing preventive and regulatory responses that can keep pace with emerging risks affecting children and adolescents.

Data availability statement

The datasets presented in this study can be found in online repositories. The names of the repository/repositories and accession number(s) can be found below: <https://zenodo.org/records/17909334>.

Ethics statement

The studies involving humans were approved by Ethics Commission for Science and Research of the Faculty of Education, Palacký University Olomouc (Approval No. 2025019). The studies were conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements. Written informed consent for participation in this study was provided by the participants' legal guardians/next of kin.

Author contributions

KK: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. DV: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. RS: Writing – review & editing. JK: Writing – review & editing. JN: Writing – review & editing. PD: Writing – review & editing.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. Generative AI was used for translation and for improving the linguistic quality of the manuscript.

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Appendix A

Survey Items Measuring Online Aggression and Cyberbullying Exposure

This appendix presents the exact wording of the survey items used to measure experiences of online aggression among adolescents. The items refer to experiences that occurred within the past 12 months. Respondents were instructed that online environments include social media, messaging applications, online games, email, and mobile communication. The items below are English translations of the original Czech questionnaire items.

Which of the following social media platforms or online services do you currently use?

Responses: Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Snapchat, Discord, Facebook, X, Messenger, WhatsApp, Telegram, Signal, Reddit, E-mail, SMS/MMS.

Response scale:

- 0 – Never
- 1 – Sometimes
- 2 – Often
- 3 – All the time

Types of online aggression

The following situations represent various forms of online harassment/harm. Select which of these you have experienced in the past year and how often they occurred.

Someone, via the internet or mobile phone:

- Verbally harmed you (humiliated, insulted, ridiculed, or otherwise verbally embarrassed you).
- Spread a photo intended to humiliate, ridicule, or otherwise embarrass you.
- Spread your intimate photo.
- Created a nude photo of you using AI.
- Spread a video recording intended to humiliate, ridicule, or otherwise embarrass you.
- Spread an audio recording intended to humiliate, ridicule, or otherwise embarrass you.
- Misused your profile/identity.
- Threatened or intimidated you.
- Defrauded/Scammed you (in shopping, via an advertisement, etc.).
- Blackmailed you.
- Logged into your social network account without permission.
- Harassed you (through repeated calling over a long period).
- Created a fake profile of you on a social network.

Response Scale:

- 1. It never happened to me.
- 2. Only once or twice.
- 3. About 3 times a month.

- 4. About once a week.
- 5. Several times a week.

Platform or service where the incident occurred

Question: On which platforms or services did the online aggression occur?

(Multiple answers allowed.)

- Instagram
- TikTok
- Snapchat
- Discord
- Facebook
- Facebook Messenger
- WhatsApp
- Telegram
- YouTube
- X (Twitter)
- E-mail
- SMS/MMS
- Other platform

E4. Identity of the Perpetrator

Question: Who was the person who carried out the online aggression against you?

- Classmate from the same class.
- Classmate from a different class (but the same school).
- Student from a different school.
- One of my parents.
- A teacher who teaches me.
- A teacher who does not teach me (but is from the same school).
- Someone I only know from the internet.
- A former friend.
- A former boyfriend/girlfriend I used to date.
- An adult I know (e.g., a relative).
- An adult I did not know (e.g., a classmate's parent).
- Other:
- I do not know who it was

E5. Coping and Help-Seeking

Question: How did you deal with the situation?
(Multiple answers allowed.)

- I did not tell anyone.
- I told my parents.
- I told a teacher or someone at school.
- I told my friends.
- I contacted an online counselling service.
- I contacted the police.
- I dealt with the problem in another way.